

The Design and Development of High-Performance FRP Energy-Absorbing Structures for Automotive Use

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ABSTRACT

It has been generally recognized for some time that reinforced plastics possess a high capability for absorbing energy, particularly under conditions where the energy absorber acts in the resilient, non-sacrificial mode typified by leaf springs, bumpers, steering wheels, etc. Interest in applications of this type, for automobiles in particular, has been given additional impetus by the pressing need to reduce vehicle weights which have generally escalated steadily over the years. In certain critical areas, particularly around the vehicle front-end, it may become cost-effective, from the overall system standpoint, to increase total structural cost by an identifiable amount if any accompanying weight reductions would produce cascading cost reductions in other components (such as tires, springs, shock absorbers, etc.).

The purpose of this paper is to review the case for using filamentary reinforced plastic materials in situations where the objective is to absorb energy due to relatively low-speed impacts in such a manner that the absorber does not suffer unacceptable structural degradation. In what follows, the detailed, but potentially significant, effects of material inertia, stress waves, etc., will be neglected and considerations based only upon theory of elasticity are employed.

While a great deal of work has been conducted into the fracture toughness behavior of composite materials and the maximum energy absorbed by the type of test typified by the falling weight test, comparatively few experiments have been conducted to determine the amount of strain energy which may be absorbed by a filamentary material under conditions of tension, compression and shear, prior to the onset of permanent damage. (For brevity, such energy will be referred to as "resilient".) To underline the important phenomenological differences between impact energy absorbed in fracturing a composite material compared to that which may be absorbed up to the onset of some form of permanent deformation, the paper suggests that while the impact values of FRP, as measured by tests of the Charpy type, are significantly less than those exhibited by such materials as steel, the maximum resilient strain energy may be 3-5 times higher, where the resilient strain energy density is set by the onset of yield.

It is emphasized that data derived from notched bar tests must be interpreted with a great deal of caution, since such tests are affected by dimensions, rate of stressing, temperature, degree of anisotropy, etc. Impact strengths increase as a function of glass volume-content and decrease as notch depth increases. Whereas it is generally assumed that rate of stressing causes impact strength to increase, in the presence of a notch, increased rate of stressing may reduce the impact strength.

Although the discussion is not concerned with ultimate conditions, per se, it is worthwhile to comment on some significant differences in the progressive fracture behavior of composites compared to metals. Whereas the critical stress intensity factor for metals is a strong function of thickness, this is not so far composites, particularly those comprised of mat/roving combinations. The effects of strain-rate and temperature on composite fracture behavior are also contrary to that which occurs in metals - the fracture toughness of FRP tends to increase with decreasing temperature and increasing strain rate.

The paper concludes with a detailed presentation of design examples (which draw upon the content presented) including leaf springs, bumper beams, steering wheels, etc.

FIG. 3 COMPARISON OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF STRUCTURAL METALS AND GLASS POLYESTER COMPOSITE

FIG. 5 LONGITUDINAL AND TRANSVERSE COMPOSITES

FIG. 4 COMPARISON OF STRESS STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF VARIOUS MATERIALS UP TO BEGINNING OF PERMANENT DEFORMATION

FIG. 6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPECIFIC STRAIN ENERGY AND ONSET OF PERMANENT DAMAGE

FIG 6: STRAIN ENERGY/COST RELATIONSHIP FOR E-GLASS ROVING/MAR POLYESTER

FIG 7: PULTRUDED BUMPER BEAM

